

Experimental Study on Methane Explosion Suppression Using Heptafluoropropane/Carbon Dioxide Mixed gas and Ultrafine Water Mist

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ABSTRACT:

Explosions caused by gas leakage remain a persistent hazard in coal mining operations, posing serious threats to personnel safety and production stability. To enhance explosion suppression efficiency, this study established an experimental platform to investigate the synergistic inhibitory effects of a heptafluoropropane/carbon dioxide (C_3HF_7/CO_2) mixed gas and ultrafine water mist on methane explosions. A series of controlled tests were conducted to analyze variations in key explosion parameters, including overpressure, flame propagation velocity, and flame morphology, under different suppression conditions. The results show that the suppression performance of the C_3HF_7/CO_2 mixture depends strongly on its composition ratio. When the heptafluoropropane volume fraction is below 40%, a positive synergistic effect occurs between heptafluoropropane and carbon dioxide, whereas higher proportions lead to a negative synergy due to the temperature-dependent radical inhibition of heptafluoropropane. Moreover, the combination of the mixed gas with ultrafine water mist produces a coupling effect that enhances both physical cooling and chemical inhibition, significantly reducing explosion intensity and flame propagation speed.

This research elucidates the cooperative suppression mechanism between the C_3HF_7/CO_2 mixed gas and ultrafine water mist, providing theoretical insights and experimental support for the development of advanced methane explosion suppression technologies in coal mine environments..

Keywords: Ultra-fine water mist, Carbon dioxide (CO_2), Heptafluoropropane (HFC-227ea), Methane Explosions Suppression, Flame propagation.

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INTRODUCTION

Methane is widely used as a clean and efficient fuel and chemical feedstock in both industry and everyday life [1,2]. However, it is also highly flammable and explosive. If a leak occurs in an enclosed area—such as in residential or industrial settings—and methane accumulates to a certain concentration in the air, even a small ignition source can trigger an explosion, leading to severe injuries, fatalities, and significant property damage [3]. However, as coal mine tunneling and extraction progress, various safety incidents may occur, posing serious threats to workers' personal safety. Among these, gas explosion accidents account for 5.17% of the total number of incidents, yet they are responsible for 40.31% of all fatalities [4].

According to statistics from the National Mine Safety Administration, between 2002 and 2019, casualties caused by gas-related accidents in coalmines accounted for one-third of all injuries and deaths resulting from coalmine incidents. In 2005 alone, there were 414 such accidents, resulting in 2,171 deaths—an average of 1.13 incidents per day [5,6]. At present, measures to address gas (methane) explosions mainly include preventive measures before accidents and suppression measures during accidents. Preventive measures primarily involve gas drainage in mines, monitoring of gas concentration and temperature, and optimization of the ventilation system. For explosion suppression, coalmines mainly adopt explosion-blocking technologies and explosion isolation measures. Once a gas explosion occurs, these suppression methods are used to prevent the propagation of flames and reduce the affected area of the explosion [7,8].

These isolation measures are mostly passive suppression techniques, relying on the shock wave generated by the explosion to disperse the suppressant agents stored in the devices into the air, thereby achieving the goal of suppressing methane explosions. However, such methods cannot suppress explosions effectively or accurately [9].

Although these preventive and suppression measures are already well developed, gas explosion accidents still occur. This is primarily because the mine is a complex working environment, with many obstacles and highly uneven distribution of gas. Methane may accumulate in certain areas, and once an ignition source appears in these regions, an explosion is likely to happen. Therefore, research into technologies for suppressing gas explosions remains highly necessary.

Relevant scholars have conducted many studies on measures to inhibit methane explosion [7]. By using different explosive inhibitors to inhibit methane explosion, the mechanisms of action of these explosive inhibitors can be divided into physical inhibition and chemical inhibition. The explosion inhibitors mainly consist of ultrafine water mist and inert gas; the explosion inhibitors mainly consist of powders, inorganic salts and fluoro-containing alkanes [10], etc. Usually, scholars use examples to improve the efficiency of explosion inhibition and will combine different explosion inhibitors to conduct methane explosion inhibition experiments.

Before 2005, halon fire extinguishing agents have been widely used in fire extinguishing and explosion suppression experiments due to their excellent fire extinguishing and explosion suppression performance, but they have been banned due to environmental reasons [11]. Therefore, finding alternatives to clean and efficient halon fire extinguishing agents has always attracted widespread attention from relevant scholars. Because the use of fine water mist will not cause pollution to the environment, the extremely high specific heat capacity makes fine water mist cooler the flame and has little damage to the protective object. These advantages make fine water mist a hot topic for many scholars to study, and gradually expand its application scope, becoming the main fire extinguishing and explosion inhibitor on the market [12].

In recent years, the second generation of fine water mist fire-extinguishing technology ultra-fine water mist has entered people's vision. The reason why ultrafine water mist has gained popularity is that ultrafine water mist not only has the characteristics of ordinary fine water mist, but also has the characteristics of fluidity like gas or smoke and consumes very little water, which makes ultrafine water mist more and more widely used [13].

At the same time, in order to improve the explosion suppression efficiency of ultrafine water mist, this paper selects heptafluoropropane/carbon dioxide mixed gas to jointly inhibit methane explosion with ultrafine water mist. Heptafluoropropane is a common fire-extinguishing agent on the market.

Compared with halogenated alkyl fire extinguishing agents, heptafluoropropane does not contain chlorine or bromine elements, so it is not harmful to the environment. It is also regarded as an excellent halon alternative [14].

At present, the frequently used inert gas explosion inhibitors (carbon dioxide and nitrogen) will only show a good explosion inhibition effect under higher volume fractions, while heptafluoropropane is mainly chemically inhibited, so the explosion inhibition efficiency is higher. Therefore, this paper improves the explosion suppression effect of carbon dioxide and ultra-fine water mist by introducing heptafluoropropane, which is to achieve the requirements of efficient explosion suppression, and ensures economically [15].

Current Status of Pure Ultrafine Water Mist Inhibits Methane Explosion

[16] tested the inhibitory effect of ultrafine water mist on methane explosion under different spray conditions. The results show that the explosion flame has higher brightness under the suppression of ultrafine water mist. When the ultrafine water mist is in a moving state, it may cause turbulence at the front of the flame and aggravate methane explosion. At the same time, as the particle size of ultrafine water mist increases, the various parameters of methane explosion also increase, so it is concluded that excessive particle size of ultrafine water mist will promote methane explosion.

[17] used simulation software to conduct a detailed analysis of ultrafine water mist suppressing methane explosion. The simulation results showed that when the particle size of ultrafine water mist is 10-15 μm , the parameters of methane explosion dropped the largest. When the ultrafine water mist particle size is greater than 50 μm , the droplets that have not completely evaporated will completely pass through the flame and cause the methane explosion intensity to increase.

[18] conducted experiments on inhibiting methane explosion by ultrafine water mist of different particle sizes, and the experiments showed that the effect of the particle size of the fine water mist on the explosion inhibition effect is crucial. Only when the explosion pressure reaches a certain value can the droplets break and decompose, thereby achieving a better inhibitory effect. Moreover, the smaller the particle size of the droplets, the greater the decrease in each parameter of methane explosion.

[19] conducted an experiment on superfine water mist to suppress methane explosion through an experimental platform built by themselves. According to experimental data, it was found that the degree of attenuation of methane explosion is directly related to the amount of ultra-fine water mist spray, the length of spray time, and the position of the spray. It was pointed out that when the amount of ultra-fine water mist spray is insufficient, the flame propagation will be accelerated and the conclusion that methane explosion will be promoted.

Research Status of Ultrafine Water Mist Containing Inorganic Salts to Inhibit Methane Explosion

[20] added different inorganic salts (NaHCO_3 , NaCl , and KCl) to the fine water mist to inhibit methane explosion. The results show that ultrafine water mist can significantly prolong the induction period of methane explosion, causing the explosion pressure and explosion speed to significantly reduce. However, when inorganic salts are added to the ultrafine water mist, the inhibitory effect on methane explosion is more obvious.

[21] conducted ultrafine water mist inhibit methane explosion experiments containing KOH , NaOH and NaCl , respectively. The experimental results show that KOH has the greatest improvement in the explosion suppression efficiency of ultrafine water mist, followed by NaCl and finally NaOH .

[22] studied the effects of various salt additives on fire extinguishing efficiency of fine water mist. Compared with pure water, the actual extinguishing time of the 10% KHCO_3 solution is shortened by 96%, the effect of other additives tested is less obvious, and some inorganic salts can even increase the extinguishing time of the ultra-fine water mist.

[23] combined alkali metal additives with ultrafine water mist to inhibit hydrogen explosion. The author believes that the two explosion inhibitory mechanisms are mainly two aspects: additives participate in the chain reaction of flame combustion and ultrafine water mist to physically inhibit

these two aspects. Moreover, only when the ultra-fine water mist evaporates quickly can alkali metal additives work better.

[24] focused on the inhibitory effect of ultrafine water mist containing metal chloride on methane explosion. When the mass fractions of different metal oxides are the same, the explosion suppression effect is arranged from large to small. The explosion suppression effect is $FeCl_2 > MnCl_2 > KCl > NaCl > CaCl_2 > MgCl_2$, and as the mass fraction of metal oxide increases, the explosion suppression effect of ultrafine water mist gradually increases.

Current Status of Research on Ultrafine Water Mist Synergistic Inert Gas to Inhibit Methane Explosion

[25] studied the coordinated suppression of hydrogen explosion between nitrogen and ultrafine water mist. Through the research results, it was found that nitrogen and ultrafine water mist can significantly affect the flame propagation speed and explosion pressure of hydrogen explosion. At the same time, it is believed that nitrogen and ultrafine water mist have a coupling effect on the inhibition of methane explosion, and the addition of nitrogen can significantly improve the explosion suppression efficiency of ultrafine water mist.

[26] studied the effect of carbon dioxide, nitrogen, helium and argon in concert with ultrafine water mist to inhibit methane explosion. From the experiment, we can see that the addition of inert gas can effectively improve the fire extinguishing and explosion suppression ability of ultra-fine water mist, and the various parameters of methane explosion are greatly reduced. Among them, carbon dioxide and ultrafine water mist have the best synergy effect, followed by nitrogen, and finally helium and argon.

[27,28] conducted experiments on inhibiting methane explosion by ultrafine water mist and nitrogen, carbon dioxide and argon respectively. According to the changes in the overpressure of methane explosion, it is concluded that the larger the specific heat capacity, the stronger the inhibitory effect on methane explosion, and the slower the flame propagation speed.

[29,30] investigated the use of nitrogen combined with ultrafine water mist to suppress hydrogen explosions. Their experiments demonstrated that the synergistic effect of nitrogen and ultrafine water mist was stronger than that of either agent alone, and this combination was highly effective in suppressing combustion in fuel-rich conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY ON THE SYNERGISTIC SUPPRESSION OF METHANE EXPLOSIONS USING HEPTAFLUOROPROPANE/CARBON DIOXIDE MIXED GASES AND FINE WATER MIST

Experimental Working Conditions

By adjusting various working conditions, the suppression effect of heptafluoropropane/carbon dioxide combined with ultrafine water mist (in a 1:4 volume ratio) on methane explosions was investigated, as detailed in Table 1. The results showed that ignition of the combustible gas did not occur when the heptafluoropropane volume fraction was at least 4% and the carbon dioxide volume fraction was at least 16%. In contrast, ignition was possible only when the heptafluoropropane content was 3% or lower and the carbon dioxide content was 12% or less.

Table1. Experimental Conditions and Ignition Results

Condition	HFC-227ea +CO ₂ (%) + Ultrafine Water Mist (mL)	Ignition Result	Condition	HFC-227ea +CO ₂ (%) + Ultrafine Water Mist (mL)	Ignition Result
Cond.1	2%+8%+1.4mL	Success	Cond.11	4%+16%+1.4mL	Fail
Cond.2	2%+8%+4.2mL	Success	Cond.12	4%+16%+4.2mL	Fail
Cond.3	2%+8%+7.0mL	Success	Cond.13	4%+16%+7.0mL	Fail
Cond.4	2%+8%+9.8mL	Success	Cond.14	4%+16%+9.8mL	Fail
Cond.5	2%+8%+12.6mL	Success	Cond.15	4%+16%+12.6mL	Fail
Cond.6	3%+12%+1.4mL	Success	Cond.16	5%+20%+1.4mL	Fail
Cond.7	3%+12%+4.2mL	Success	Cond.17	5%+20%+4.2mL	Fail

Cond.8	3%+12%+7.0mL	Success	Cond.18	5%+20%+7.0mL	Fail
Cond.9	3%+12%+9.8mL	Success	Cond.19	5%+20%+9.8mL	Fail
Cond.10	3%+12%+12.6mL	Success	Cond.20	5%+20%+12.6mL	Fail

Effect of Heptafluoropropane/Carbon Dioxide Mixed Gas Combined with Ultrafine Water Mist on the Flame Propagation Shape of Methane Explosion

Figure 1 compares the flame structures of a 9.5% methane/air explosion under different suppression conditions: 12% CO₂, 3% heptafluoropropane + 12% CO₂, and the same gas mixture with 4.2 mL ultrafine water mist.

The flame typically evolves through hemispherical, finger-like, planar, and tulip-shaped stages. However, with the addition of heptafluoropropane, the tulip flame disappears—likely due to its chemical inhibition effect. Heptafluoropropane decomposes into fluorinated radicals that capture free radicals in the flame, disrupt the reverse pressure wave, and suppress tulip-shaped flame formation. The addition of 12% CO₂ slightly increases flame brightness and introduces yellow coloration due to reduced flame temperature from heat absorption. When 3% heptafluoropropane was added alongside 12% CO₂, the flame becomes dimmer, pale yellow patches appear, and flame propagation slows significantly. This indicates a positive synergistic inhibition effect, where the combined agents reduce the combustion reaction rate more effectively than CO₂ alone.

Figure1. Flame Propagation Situation

Figure1 also shows that the combination of ultrafine water mist with the heptafluoropropane/carbon dioxide mixed gas further suppresses flame propagation during a methane explosion. As the flame reaches similar positions, the time taken increases significantly. As shown in Figure1 (b, c, and d) the time for the flame to reach the left end of the tube is 300 ms, 520 ms, and 817 ms respectively—

representing increases of 200%, 420%, and 717% compared to the 9.5% methane/air mixture. Additionally, when using this combined suppression method, multiple ignition attempts may be required to ignite the 9.5% methane/air mixture. Compared to ultrafine water mist alone, the mixed gases distribute more evenly, diffuse more rapidly, and do not exhibit settling or agglomeration.

In the early stage of combustion, the synergy between heptafluoropropane and carbon dioxide consumes a large number of active free radicals in the explosion chain reaction, reducing the flame reaction rate and slowing flame propagation. This allows more time for water mist to evaporate, further decreasing the combustion rate.

Effect of Heptafluoropropane/Carbon Dioxide Mixed Gas Synergistic Ultrafine Water Mist on Methane Explosion Pressure and Average Boost Rate

Figure 2 presents the explosion pressure and average pressure-rise rate curves for a 9.5% methane–air mixture under the combined suppression of two gas mixtures (2% C₃HF₇/ 8% CO₂ and 3% C₃HF₇/ 12% CO₂) with varying superfine water mist volumes.

Figure 2. Variation of Methane Explosion Overpressure under Different Conditions

As the mist volume increases, the slope of the pressure-rise curve decreases and the peak overpressure drops significantly. Under conditions 5, 7, and 8, a plateau appears in the pressure curve, indicating a temporary stagnation of flame propagation at specific locations within the tube. Post-experiment inspection revealed water residue at these positions. This suggests uneven distribution of the suppression agents, with mist concentration highest near the spray nozzle—consistent with the observed water accumulation.

Figure 3. Variation of Methane Explosion Peak over Pressure and Time to Peak under Different Conditions

Figure 3 presents the peak explosion overpressure and time to peak pressure for a 9.5% methane–air mixture suppressed by two gas agent combinations: 2% C₃H₇F/ 8% CO₂ and 3% C₃H₇F/ 12% CO₂, each combined with varying volumes of superfine water mist.

For the 2% C₃H₇F/ 8% CO₂ mixture, the initial peak overpressure of 22.45 kPa was reduced to 18.24 kPa, 13.45 kPa, 8.31 kPa, 5.24 kPa, and 3.77 kPa with 1.4, 4.2, 7.0, 9.8, and 12.6 mL of water mist, respectively—corresponding to reductions of 18.75%, 40.10%, 62.98%, 76.66%, and 83.21%. Concurrently, the time to peak increased from 135 ms to 200 ms, 260 ms, 352 ms, 418 ms, and 546 ms—an extension of up to 304.4%. In the case of the 3% C₃H₇F/ 12% CO₂ mixture, peak pressure decreased from 13.9 kPa to 10.74 kPa, 5.31 kPa, and 2.89 kPa with 1.4, 4.2, and 7.0 mL of mist (reductions of 22.7%, 61.8%, and 79.2%). The time to peak extended from 234 ms to 374 ms, 473 ms, and 576 ms—up to a 146.2% increase.

These results indicate a strong synergistic suppression effect between ultrafine water mist and the gas mixtures. However, the marginal benefit diminishes as mist volume increases, likely due to the mist’s “barrier effect” [31], which may hinder the dispersion of suppressant gases and reduce flame-agent interaction efficiency.

Figure 4. Variation in the Average Rate of Pressure Rise during Methane Explosions under Different Conditions

Figure 4 shows the variation in the average rate of pressure rise during the explosion of a 9.5% methane–air mixture suppressed by two gas mixtures—2% heptafluoropropane/ 8% carbon dioxide and 3% heptafluoropropane/12% carbon dioxide—combined with varying volumes of superfine water mist.

When 2% C₃H₇F/8% CO₂ was used with increasing amounts of water mist (1.4, 4.2, 7.0, 9.8, and 12.6 mL), the average rate of pressure rise decreased from 92.1 kPa·s⁻¹ to 6.9 kPa·s⁻¹, corresponding to reductions of 85.7%, 92.5%, 96.6%, 98.2%, and 99.0%, respectively, compared to the methane–air baseline. Similarly, with 3% C₃H₇F/12% CO₂ and water mist volumes of 1.4, 4.2, and 7.0 mL, the average pressure rise rate dropped to 16.6, 6.5, and 3.3 kPa·s⁻¹, achieving reductions of 97.6%, 99.1%, and 99.5%, respectively.

These results indicate that, at constant gas mixture concentrations, increasing the volume of ultrafine water mist significantly enhances the suppression efficiency of the gas mixtures against methane explosions.

Effect of Heptafluoropropane/Carbon Dioxide Mixed Gas Combined with Superfine Water Mist on Methane Explosion Flame Propagation Speed and Position

Figure 5 compares the flame propagation speed over time during the explosion of a 9.5% methane–air mixture under the suppression of two gas mixtures—2% heptafluoropropane/8% carbon dioxide

and 3% heptafluoropropane/12% carbon dioxide—combined with varying volumes of superfine water mist.

Figure 5. Variation of Methane Explosion Flame Speed under Different Conditions

The flame speed curves initially increase and then decrease over time. Under conditions 1, 2, 3, and 6, a rapid initial rise in flame speed is observed. This behavior is attributed to the hemispherical flame expanding quickly in the early propagation stage, causing a sharp increase in speed until the flame contacts the tube wall. At this point, heat loss to the wall reduces the flame temperature, slowing the rate of increase. As the explosion proceeds, the flame accelerates again, reaching its maximum speed simultaneously with the peak pressure. Afterward, the flame speed declines until it exits the tube.

Under conditions 4, 5, 7, and 8, the flame speed remains relatively stable without significant fluctuations. This likely result from the increased volume fractions of the gas mixtures and superfine water mist, which lower the flame temperature in the early stage. Here, the suppressant effect mainly arises from the heptafluoropropane and carbon dioxide mixture. In the later stage, the superior physical properties of the superfine water mist become more effective, jointly inhibiting the methane explosion with the gas mixture.

Therefore, when the gas mixture fraction is low, increasing the superfine water mist volume can achieve the desired suppression effect. Conversely, if the water mist volume is small, increasing the gas mixture fraction can also enhance suppression performance.

Figure 6 shows that when the volume fraction of the gas mixture remains constant, increasing the amount of superfine water mist results in a gradual decrease in both the peak flame propagation speed and the rate of increase during methane explosion.

With 2% C_3HF_7 / 8% CO_2 and increasing mist volumes of 1.4, 4.2, 7.0, 9.8, and 12.6 mL, the maximum flame speeds were 14.23, 11.54, 7.48, 5.34, and 4.50 m/s, corresponding to reductions of 24.5%, 38.7%, 60.3%, 71.7%, and 76.1% compared to the baseline methane explosion. For the 3% C_3HF_7 / 12% CO_2 mixture with 1.4, 4.2, and 7.0 mL of mist, the peak flame speeds were reduced to 8.84, 5.67, and 3.28 m/s—decreases of 52.8%, 69.7%, and 82.5%, respectively. These results demonstrate a synergistic inhibitory effect between the heptafluoropropane/ CO_2 mixtures and ultrafine water mist. However, as mist volume increases, the “barrier effect” of the water mist may limit agent dispersion, thereby weakening this synergy.

Figure 6. Variation of Methane Explosion Propagation Speed under Different Conditions

Figure 7. Flame Front Position of Methane Explosion under Different Conditions

Figure 7 shows the flame front position over time during the explosion of a 9.5% methane–air mixture, suppressed by 2% C₃HF₇/ 8% CO₂ and 3% C₃HF₇/ 12% CO₂ gas mixtures combined with varying volumes of superfine water mist.

The slope of the flame position–time curves clearly reflects the flame propagation trend. As seen in the figure, at any given moment, the flame front distance decreases with increasing mist volume. Additionally, the slope of the curves progressively decreases, indicating that the combination of the gas mixtures and ultrafine water mist has a synergistic inhibitory effect on methane explosion propagation.

CONCLUSION

Reducing gas leakage and preventing fire and explosion hazards in mine tunnels remain critical challenges in coal mining. This study utilized a specialized experimental platform to evaluate the inhibitory effects of explosion-suppression media on methane explosions by examining changes in explosion overpressure, flame propagation speed, and flame morphology.

The results show that mixing heptafluoropropane and carbon dioxide produces a synergistic suppression effect that depends on their volume ratio. When the proportion of heptafluoropropane is below 40%, a positive synergy occurs, enhancing explosion inhibition. However, when the

proportion exceeds 40%, the synergy becomes negative. This is because heptafluoropropane reduces free radicals through chemical inhibition that is more effective at high temperatures; at lower temperatures, its ability to bind with flame radicals weakens, diminishing the overall suppression efficiency.

Furthermore, a coupling effect exists between the C_3HF_7/CO_2 mixed gas and ultrafine water mist. Due to the faster diffusion of the gas mixture compared with the mist, the gases act first to slow the early flame development and lower the temperature in the explosion channel. This delay allows the ultrafine water mist to evaporate more fully and remain longer in the system, thereby enhancing its cooling and radical-quenching effects. Together, these interactions significantly reduce methane explosion intensity and flame propagation within mine tunnels.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Caballero and P. J. Pérez, "Methane as raw material in synthetic chemistry: the final frontier," *Chemical Society Reviews*, vol. 42, no. 23, pp. 8809–8820, 2013. doi:10.1039/C3CS60120J
- [2] P. Balcombe, K. Anderson, J. Speirs, N. Brandon, and A. Hawkes, "The natural gas supply chain: the importance of methane and carbon dioxide emissions," *ACS Sustainable Chemistry & Engineering*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 3–20, 2017. doi:10.1021/acssuschemeng.6b00144
- [3] S. Kundu, J. Zanganeh, and B. Moghtaderi, "A review on understanding explosions from methane–air mixture," *Journal of Loss Prevention in the Process Industries*, vol. 40, pp. 507–523, 2016. doi:10.1016/j.jlp.2016.02.004
- [4] J. H. Saleh and A. M. Cummings, "Safety in the mining industry and the unfinished legacy of mining accidents: Safety levers and defense-in-depth for addressing mining hazards," *Safety Science*, vol. 49, no. 6, pp. 764–777, 2011. doi:10.1016/j.ssci.2011.02.017
- [5] L. Wang, Y.-P. Cheng, and H.-Y. Liu, "An analysis of fatal gas accidents in Chinese coal mines," *Safety Science*, vol. 62, pp. 107–113, 2014. doi:10.1016/j.ssci.2013.08.010
- [6] X. Wang, L. Qian, D. Li, et al., "Incidence, casualties and risk characteristics of civilian explosion blast injury in China: 2000–2017 data from the State Administration of Work Safety," *Military Medical Research*, vol. 7, no. 29, 2020. doi:10.1186/s40779-020-00257-5
- [7] J. J. L. du Plessis and H. Späth, "Active explosion barrier performance against methane and coal dust explosions," *International Journal of Coal Science & Technology*, vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 261–268, 2015. doi:10.1007/s40789-015-0097-7
- [8] L. Li, T. Liu, Z. Li, X. Chen, L. Wang, and S. Feng, "Different prevention effects of ventilation dilution on methane accumulation at high temperature zone in coal mine goafs," *Energies*, vol. 16, no. 7, 3168, 2023. doi:10.3390/en16073168
- [9] Z. Huang, R. Si, G. Wen, S. Jin, and S. Xue, "Experimental study on the isolation effect of an active flameproof device on a gas explosion in an underground coal mine," *Fire*, vol. 6, no. 12, 468, 2023. doi:10.3390/fire6120468
- [10] X. Y. Cao, M. S. Bi, J. J. Ren, and B. Chen, "Experimental research on explosion suppression affected by ultrafine water mist containing different additives," *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, vol. 368, pp. 613–620, 2019. doi:10.1016/j.jhazmat.2019.01.006
- [11] Y. Wang, G. Zou, C. Liu, and Y. Gao, "Comparison of fire extinguishing performance of four halon substitutes and Halon 1301," *Journal of Fire Sciences*, vol. 39, no. 5, pp. 370–399, 2021. doi:10.1177/073490412111030188
- [12] Z. Wang, Y. Zhang, J. Wang, Y. Liu, H. Hou, R. Pan, and X. Zhou, "Study of thermal pyrolysis characteristics and fire extinguishing performance of novel halon alternatives for aviation applications," *Journal of Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry*, vol. 150, no. 15, pp. 11591–11609, 2025. doi:10.1007/s10973-024-13363-6
- [13] K. Farrell, M. K. Hassan, M. D. Hossain, B. Ahmed, P. Rahnamayiezekavat, G. Douglas, and S.

- Saha, "Water mist fire suppression systems for building and industrial applications: issues and challenges," *Fire*, vol. 6, no. 2, 40, 2023. doi:10.3390/fire6020040
- [14] B. Pei, S. Wei, L. Chen, R. Pan, M. Yu, and G. Jing, "Synergistic inhibition effect on the self-acceleration characteristics in the initial stage of methane/air explosion by CO₂ and ultrafine water mist," *RSC Advances*, vol. 9, pp. 13940–13948, 2019. doi:10.1039/C9RA01148J
- [15] W. Tan, D. Lü, L. Liu, G. Zhu, and N. Jiang, "Suppression of methane/air explosion by water mist with potassium halide additives driven by CO₂," *Chinese Journal of Chemical Engineering*, vol. 27, no. 11, pp. 2742–2748, 2019. doi:10.1016/j.cjche.2019.03.020
- [16] P. Zhang, Y. Zhou, X. Cao, X. Gao, and M. Bi, "Enhancement effects of methane/air explosion caused by water spraying in a sealed vessel," *Journal of Loss Prevention in the Process Industries*, vol. 29, pp. 313–318, 2014. doi:10.1016/j.jlp.2014.03.014
- [17] X. Cao, J. Ren, M. Bi, et al., "Effect of droplet size on the inhibition of methane/air explosion process by ultrafine water mist," *Journal of China Coal Society*, vol. 42, no. 9, pp. 2376–2384, 2017. doi:10.13225/j.cnki.jccs.2016.1387
- [18] K. V. Wingerden, "Mitigation of gas explosions using water deluge," *Process Safety Progress*, vol. 19, no. 3, pp. 173–178, 2000. doi:10.1002/prs.680190309
- [19] L. Chen, R. Zong, S. Li, et al., "Experimental study on the effectiveness of ultrafine water mist suppressing confined space bombing," *Journal of China University of Science and Technology*, 2009, no. 7, pp. 777–782. doi:Unavailable
- [20] X. Chen, Y. Lin, Z. Luo, et al., "Experimental study on controlling gas explosion by water-based inhibitors," *Acta Coal Sinica*, vol. 31, no. 5, pp. 603–606, 2006. doi:Unavailable
- [21] H. K. Chelliah, A. K. Lazzarini, P. C. Wanigarathne, et al., "Inhibition of premixed and non-premixed flames with fine droplets of water and solutions," *Proceedings of the Combustion Institute*, vol. 29, no. 1, pp. 369–376, 2002. doi:10.1016/S1540-7489(02)80048-7
- [22] P. Joseph, E. Nichols, and V. Novozhilov, "A comparative study of the effects of chemical additives on the suppression efficiency of water mist," *Fire Safety Journal*, vol. 58, pp. 221–225, 2013. doi:10.1016/j.firesaf.2013.03.003
- [23] J. M. Ingram, A. F. Averill, P. Battersby, et al., "Suppression of hydrogen/oxygen/nitrogen explosions by fine water mist containing sodium hydroxide additive," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 38, no. 19, pp. 8002–8010, 2013. doi:10.1016/j.ijhydene.2013.04.048
- [24] L. G. Liu, B. H. Cong, et al., "Experimental evaluation of water mist with metal chloride additives for suppressing CH₄/air cup-burner flames," *Journal of Thermal Science*, vol. 22, no. 3, pp. 269–274, 2013. doi:10.1007/s11630-013-0623-0
- [25] J. M. Ingram, A. F. Averill, P. N. Battersby, et al., "Suppression of hydrogen–oxygen–nitrogen explosions by fine water mist: Part 1. Burning velocity," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 37, no. 24, pp. 19250–19257, 2012. doi:10.1016/j.ijhydene.2012.09.092
- [26] B. Pei, H. Lyu, M. Wu, et al., "Synergistic effect of gas-liquid two-phase medium inhibits the methane explosion in pipeline," *Acta Coal Sinica*, vol. 43, no. 11, pp. 3130–3136, 2018. doi:10.13225/j.cnki.jccs.2018.0064
- [27] B. Galmiche, F. Halter, F. Foucher, and P. Dagaut, "Effects of dilution on laminar burning velocity of premixed methane/air flames," *Energy & Fuels*, vol. 25, no. 3, pp. 948–954, 2011. doi:10.1021/ef101482d
- [28] W. Tan, L. Dong, L. Liu, et al., "Suppression of methane/air explosion by water mist with potassium halide additives driven by CO₂," *Chinese Journal of Chemical Engineering*, vol. 27, no. 11, pp. 2742–2748, 2019. doi:10.1016/j.cjche.2019.03.020
- [29] P. G. Holborn, P. Battersby, J. M. Ingram, A. F. Averill, and P. F. Nolan, "Estimating the effect of water fog and nitrogen dilution upon the burning velocity of hydrogen deflagrations from experimental test data," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 38, no. 16, pp. 6882–6895,

2013. doi:10.1016/j.ijhydene.2013.03.063

[30] P. G. Holborn, P. N. Battersby, J. M. Ingram, A. F. Averill, and P. F. Nolan, "Modelling the mitigation of lean hydrogen deflagrations in a vented cylindrical rig with water fog," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 37, no. 20, pp. 15406–15422, 2012. doi:10.1016/j.ijhydene.2012.07.131

[31] B. Pei, H. Lyu, Z. Wu, et al., "Study on the synergistic effect of inert gas and ultrafine water mist on hydrogen explosion suppression," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 82, pp. 531–543, 2024. doi:10.1016/j.ijhydene.2024.07.451

